

Representing SME Creditworthiness in Society 5.0

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Abstract. Society 5.0 envision a human-centered society that balances economic advancement and the resolution of social problems by a system that highly integrates cyberspace and physical space. This exploratory paper focuses on SME limited access to credit. Access to financing is a significant social issue for society in eradicating poverty and achieving economic equality. Despite their significant contribution, credit constraints hinder SME's growth and development. We present our argument that conventional financial institution representation on SME creditworthiness may not be sufficient to mitigate the information asymmetry issue in serving the SME lending market. This exploratory paper investigates the challenges in representing SME creditworthiness and proposed a solution to mitigate the issue. Society 5.0 agenda presents an opportunity to reengineer creditworthiness representation because of newly available technology in collecting, analyzing and sharing data. Since the process requires an intelligent agent to interact with the accumulated knowledge for reasoning and decision-making purposes, a knowledge representation of SME creditworthiness is necessary to achieve the agenda.

Keywords: SME, Creditworthiness, Knowledge Representation.

1 Introduction

Access to financing is one of the significant social issues that become a constraint to society. Leaders are designing agendas and strategies to reduce economic and financial disparities with the financial inclusion initiative [1]. Financial inclusion is a significant building block for poverty reduction and economic growth. The ultimate goal is to improve the overall quality of the societies lives by allowing them to use financial services [2]. One of the significant debates on financial inclusion is SME access to financing. The financial inclusion market presents an enormous opportunity potentially from banking underbanked SMEs [3].

SMEs will open economic opportunities worth USD12 trillion and create 380 million jobs by 2030, with more than 50 per cent of the opportunity located in developing countries [4]. The SME spectrum plays a prominent role in social-economic development. The sector contributes to national income, employment, productivity, support large enterprises and encourage entrepreneurship [5]. Despite their significant importance, access to financing remains a primary constraint for SME development in

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developed and emerging economies. The sector requires access to financing for their creation, survival and growth [6].

Society 5.0 envision an ideal form of the future ‘super-smart society’ through a high degree of merging between cyberspace and physical space and leveraging ICT. The concept necessitates a balance of economic advancement and the resolution of social problems. The usage of IR4.0 technology will perform a role as an agent that supports the smart-society, thereby optimizing the entire social and organizational system [7]. Society 5.0 will feature an iterative cycle in which data are gathered from the real-world, analyzed in cyberspace, and converted into meaningful information to derive real-world solutions for managing or improving society. The cycle emphasis on knowledge accumulation and sharing on a societal level to allow continuous improvement [8].

Society 5.0 present an opportunity to achieve balanced economic development and resolve the social issue, mainly around poverty and economic inequality. Therefore, SME limited access to financing is a significant issue that needs to be solved. We present our argument that conventional financial institution representation on SME creditworthiness may not be sufficient to mitigate the information asymmetry issue in serving the SME lending market. This exploratory paper explores the issue of representing SME creditworthiness and proposed a solution according to Society 5.0 recommendation.

This paper is organized into six different sections. In section 2, the paper explores the fundamental problem of lending and factors contributing to the information asymmetry in serving SME borrower. Section 3 discusses the methodology applied to conceptualize the solution to solve the issue according to Society 5.0 vision. Section 4 provides a recommendation on formulating a knowledge representation of SME creditworthiness to mitigate the information asymmetry issue. Section 5 discuss the general characteristics expected of the knowledge representation of SME creditworthiness. Finally, the last section summarizes the exploratory paper and discusses future research and limitation.

2 Literature Background

In this section, the discussion begins by exploring literature about SME borrower characteristic, the concept of creditworthiness and the impact of information asymmetry in lending. The literature provides an overview of the lending phenomena in serving underserved borrower.

2.1 SME Access to Financing

SME faces structural challenges due to information asymmetries, and the sector is deemed to be lacking in financial skills and knowledge [6]. Lending business to SME risky even if default probabilities are heterogeneous across maturities, regions and risk levels. SMEs poor-credit assessment, lack of collateral, incomplete documentation and lack of credit history have made the banks reluctant to lend. Fluctuation in income or

earnings volatility causes high uncertainty on returns and has severe implication on SME credit quality [9].

High uncertainty and vague credit status have prompted the bank to credit ration the sector to reduce the potential risk of credit losses. Credit rationing has become a bottleneck that restricts SME growth and development [10]. The opaqueness of the firms makes it very difficult for SME to obtain formal credit. The banks require transparent information regarding the financial health of the firm. The majority of the SMEs do not maintain decent financial statements of their transactions and operate in an opaque manner. Therefore, the banks and financial institutions hesitate to provide credit to SMEs because of information asymmetry that leads to adverse selection and moral hazard issues [11].

The foundation of the decision-making processes on lending depends on economic data. SME limited data contribute to the information asymmetry problem [12], results in higher risk and discourages bank lending [13]. Opacity and uncertainty of SMEs characteristic have led to unfavorable creditworthiness value. Conventional banking requirement for formal credit could not fit the underserved SME borrower. The literature supports our argument that the bank representation on SME creditworthiness is not sufficient to mitigate information asymmetry in this risky segment.

2.2 Information Asymmetry Impact on Creditworthiness

The money lending business will always be affected by credit risk. There will be an element of uncertainty in credit transaction that poses a form of risk to the lenders [14]. Credit risk is a financial risk when the creditor faces losses because the borrower does not repay their debt obligations [15]. Therefore, an important aspect of the lending business is credit evaluation to determine repayment probabilities. Borrower's creditworthiness provides the basis for the lending decision and the pricing and structuring of the loan agreement [16].

The ultimate purpose of credit analysis is to assess the borrower creditworthiness. [17] provide an interpretation of creditworthiness as the "*economic and legal capacity of the borrower to obtain a loan and return it to the commercial bank following the terms and conditions of the agreement*". [18] indicate creditworthiness must take into account the borrower's ability to receive, efficiently using, and repaying credit. The concept of creditworthiness is significant in lending and remain the underlying factor that represents a worthy borrower. Empirical evidence suggests creditworthiness has a significant positive influence on access to finance [19].

Before receiving credit, a borrower needs a reputable credit rating. Conventional lenders want the most creditworthy borrowers to protect themselves from default risk. Information asymmetry is a form of information disconnect that affect the credit evaluation process. Information asymmetry is a concept about two transacting parties, with one party always knowing more information than the other [20]. In a perfect market theory, complete and costless information is available to both parties and no uncertainties regarding present and future trading conditions. The parties do not suffer from market failure due to the completeness of the information. However, in the real world, information is neither perfect nor costless. Thus, information asymmetry is an acute issue

in small businesses financing because of high risk and uncertainty regarding future conditions [21].

Efficient markets require a mechanism to overcome the imperfect information problem. Financial intermediaries exist to overcome market failure and resolve the information asymmetry problem. Distortion of information in credit allocation will lead to adverse selection and moral hazard problems. Adverse selection increases the probability of a loan being disbursed to borrowers with bad credit risks. Moral hazard lowers the probability of loan repayment [22]. Information asymmetry distorts borrower's creditworthiness information and the issue is more significant when it comes to SME borrower because of their characteristics.

Improving the scale and efficiency of SMEs finance requires financial innovation to improve enterprise credit systems, and promote better capital management for SMEs [23]. Therefore, the literature supports our argument that information asymmetry reduces lending market efficiency and is causing all credit rationing behaviour on SME borrower.

3 Methodology

How to represent SME creditworthiness in Society 5.0? is a fitting research question to explore the new conceptualization. This exploratory paper will utilize the integrative review to address the new emerging topics. The method provides an overview of the knowledge base, critically review and potentially reconceptualize, and expand on the theoretical foundation of the specific topic. The methodology is suitable to create initial or preliminary conceptualizations on a new topic. The review requires a more creative collection of data. The purpose is usually not to cover all articles ever published on the topic but rather to combine perspectives and insights from different fields of research traditions [45].

Although an integrative review can be conducted in many ways, researchers are still expected to follow accepted conventions for reporting on how the study was conducted [46]. Therefore, the paper explores literature to understand the concept of Society 5.0 visions to achieve economic advancement and the resolution of social problems. This paper conceptualizes the solution through knowledge representation to achieve AI and provide initial characteristics of the knowledge representation.

4 Knowledge Representation of SME Creditworthiness

Financial institution and banks require an optimal functioning credit mechanism based on the timely repayment of borrowed resources. Therefore, distributing a loan to a worthy borrower based on the credit rating approach was applied. The rating provides a general idea about the borrower and the quality of the loan portfolio. The rating approach is valuable because it requires a constant collection of updated information [17]. The purpose of credit scoring is to provide a concise and objective measure of a borrower's creditworthiness. The credit scoring system provides a firm basis for the lending decision and enhances time efficiencies making decisions [24].

Formulation of credit score or credit rating utilizes a various type of determinants. Information or data is fed into an assessment model, and the result represents the borrower creditworthiness. Lack of public information, inadequate quality and frequency of financial statements compared to large enterprises makes it difficult to assess and monitor SMEs credit risk [25]. [26] indicate managing credit risk for SMEs requires models and procedures specifically designed for SME. The conventional creditworthiness assessment model may not fit the sector.

Credit score or credit rating is the underlying borrower creditworthiness information. A finite number of determinants is applied and processed to generate a credit score. The term determinant is defined as a factor that collectively and decisively influences the probability of default or risk level of a borrower. Society 5.0 agenda on the advanced fusion of cyberspace and physical space presents an opportunity to reengineer creditworthiness representation because of new technology available in collecting, analyzing and sharing data. The process requires an intelligent agent to interact with the accumulated knowledge for reasoning and decision-making purposes. Therefore, a knowledge representation is required to represent SME creditworthiness.

Knowledge representation is a symbol used to represent propositions, built on knowledge or information. Modern computer applications use knowledge representations in various contexts, including information search, simulation, web semantic ontology description [27]. Knowledge has become the main value driver for modern organizations and a critical competitive asset. A successful knowledge representation provides a means for expressing knowledge and facilitates the inference processes in human and machines [28].

[29] elaborate knowledge representation is about understanding and describing the richness of the world, which carries five distinct roles. The function of knowledge representation act as a surrogate inside a reasoner for the things that exist in the world. It is also a set of ontological commitment that represents an approximation to reality, highlighting a specific part of the world. The focusing effect is essential because the complexity of the natural world is overwhelming. The third role for representation is as a fragmentary theory of intelligent reasoning that typically motivated by some insight indicating how people reason intelligently. Based on the pure mechanistic view, representation is a medium for efficient computation and inevitably central to the notion of representation. Finally, it is also a medium of human expression to express the world.

The goal of the representation system is common sense reasoning. There are four underlying properties to ensure a desirable representation system. The system must show representational adequacy to represent the required knowledge and inferential adequacy to manipulate the knowledge. The third properties are inferential efficiency, which refers to the ability to direct inference methods into productive directions and respond with limited resources. Finally, acquisitional efficiency refers to the ability to acquire new knowledge, ideally or automatically [30].

Designing an Artificial Intelligence (AI) problem-solving application requires strategies to solve specific problems as it will depend on one type of knowledge representation. AI requires a large amount of knowledge and a mechanism to manipulate the knowledge or information to create a solution. Specific knowledge representation models allow for more powerful inference mechanisms to guide the search for a solution

[31]. AI ability to solve a problem depends on the ability to represent knowledge about the world. AI reason with the knowledge or information to obtain meaningful answers. The development of knowledge representation must be rich and close to the predicament to express the knowledge needed to solve the problem through computational gain [32].

Knowledge representation can take the form of a knowledge model. Knowledge Modelling can simulate intelligence as envisioned in Society 5.0 to enhance innovation, progress and prosperity, and all depends heavily on making the “right decisions”. Knowledge Modelling is a critical element of cognitive discipline and a prerequisite for reaching true AI. It incorporates the quantitative and qualitative use of information and processes tangible and intangible attributes that contribute to a decision. Other benefit includes the ability to constantly monitor, improve and assist humans to learn from past decisions, assess present activities and preserve domain expertise [33].

Therefore, achieving the Society 5.0 vision in solving one of the prominent social issues through AI requires a knowledge representation of SME creditworthiness. The representation can be conceptualized into a knowledge model that enables IR 4.0 technologies to continuously improve social wellbeing and achieve balance economic development. The knowledge representation of SME creditworthiness will consist of specific domain knowledge and information that forms the knowledge model.

5 Characteristic of SME Creditworthiness Knowledge Model

The development of the SME Creditworthiness Knowledge Model must consider specific characteristic that applies to the creditworthiness domain. The model is built on knowledge and modelled for an intelligent agent to perform reasoning and decision-making. The discussion on the characteristic of the knowledge model is to ensure the applied knowledge for decision-making is valid, mature, and high quality [34]. A low-quality knowledge base will prompt the intelligent agent to make loosely based decision-making. Each knowledge is a combination of various determinant classified together into two main characteristics, including a discussion on the role of knowledge representation.

5.1 Hard-Information

The hard-information, mainly financial or standard banking ratios is a conventional but significant determinant applied in assessing borrower creditworthiness. Hard-information is information recorded as numbers such as financial statements, payment history, or quantity of output. It is in quantitative form and can easily be collected, stored, and transmitted electronically. The context during information collection is not significant, and data collection does not need to be personal [35]. Banking and other financial institutions rely heavily on hard-information to assess borrower’s creditworthiness.

There are three main dimensions of hard-information. The nature of hard-information is quantitative or a number. The collection method is impersonal or does not depend upon the context of its production, therefore hard-information exhaustive and

explicit. Finally, hard-information is not susceptible to cognitive factors such as subjective judgement, opinions and perception. Collecting hard-information is low cost and easily automated with technology. It has a comparability and verifiability element, allowing a separate process of collecting and using the information [36].

Hard-information exhibits greater inference of high grade or worthy borrowers. The creditworthiness representation is based on verified financial information applies by banks to screen borrowers [37]. Therefore, hard-information is essential in comparing creditworthiness across borrowers and categories of borrowers. It is a fundamental element in risk management mechanisms that can mitigate information asymmetry [38]. There are three different class of hard-information consist of profitability conditions, solvency and liquidity conditions and quality of credit relation. The three-class indicate business capabilities in generating profit, meeting long term and short-term financial commitment and obligation, and credit behavior.

In this section, the characteristic discussion provides an overview of hard-information. Financial information has become the basis of the credit risk assessment model across the different financial market. Hard-information has been proven theoretically and in the general practice of their reliability to gauge borrower creditworthiness. Therefore, hard-information will be the fundamental knowledge in the creditworthiness knowledge model.

5.2 Soft-Information

The role of soft-information in financial markets has grown significantly in characterizing the lending environment and influencing the design of the lending market [35]. Since SMEs are weak in financial infrastructure and lack transparency, extending credit to the sector has become an obstacle. With limited hard-information, assessing borrower creditworthiness requires the lending market to rely more heavily on soft-information [39]. Small business loans rely more on relationship lending due to a lack of hard-information [40].

There is a variety of costless information that help improve market transparency, efficiency and provide a better signal on borrower's creditworthiness. Soft-information provides valuable input in credit appraisal, and together with hard-information will improve the loan performance. The use of soft-information became a possible alternative and a complementary solution to address information asymmetry. Soft-information signals the reliability of the business owner, however, it is subjective to cognitive interpretation [41].

The soft-information capability to increase hard-information predictive power is documented in empirical research that aims at investigating the qualitative factor impact on default risk prediction. The information is in qualitative form and non-verifiable, therefore manipulable, but produces a more precise estimation of the borrower quality, despite the subjective judgment, opinions and perception [36]. The determinant can be classified into demographic characteristics and social capital, and each of the determinants influences future loan performance. The demographic characteristics consist of determinants like age, race, gender and origin. Social capital or social connectivity can be friends, groups and a picture of the borrower [42].

The interconnected nature of society in cyberspace through various social platforms has open new possibilities in expanding soft-information determinant. Information diffusion through the online network can be collected and applied in improving lending outcomes for both high and low-risk borrowers [43]. It is considered a digital footprint, and the determinant possesses a discriminatory ability to determine borrower creditworthiness. The digital footprint can be considered as a proxy for income, character and reputation and is highly valuable for default prediction [44].

In this section, the soft-information characteristic provides an overview and potential of the newly available information to enhance the credit assessment process in determining SME creditworthiness. The addition of soft-information must complement hard-information to feed the credit assessment model because of SME limited information. Therefore, this class of determinants must be applied in the knowledge model.

5.3 Role of Knowledge Representation

The final characteristic discusses the role of knowledge representation. Each role provides a characteristic view of the knowledge model in representing specific knowledge. The knowledge model must represent all the knowledge of creditworthiness pertaining to SME borrower in lending. The roles are based on [29] description and presented below.

Table 1. Role of Knowledge Representation

Role	Description	Creditworthiness Representation
Role 1	A Knowledge Representation Is a Surrogate	Functions as a surrogate inside a reasoner. The knowledge representation enables an intelligent entity to determine SME borrower creditworthiness.
Role 2	A Knowledge Representation Is a Set of Ontological Commitments	The knowledge representation is an approximation to reality, meaning the knowledge is relevant to be applied in determining SME creditworthiness.
Role 3	A Knowledge Representation Is a Fragmentary Theory of Intelligent Reasoning	Intelligent reasoning indicates how people reason intelligently. The knowledge representation will enable an intelligent entity to distinguish between worthy and unworthy SME borrower to receive their loan request.
Role 4	A Knowledge Representation Is a Medium for Efficient Computation	Reasoning in a machine is a computational process. The knowledge representation will enable the computational process of the determinants that represent SME borrower regardless of the applied assessment methodology.

Role 5	A Knowledge Representation Is a Medium of Human Expression	Medium of expressing worthy and unworthy borrower to receive funding.
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6 Conclusion

Society 5.0 agenda on the advanced fusion of cyberspace and physical space presents an opportunity to reengineer creditworthiness representation because of new technology available in collecting, analyzing and sharing knowledge. IR4.0 innovative technologies are pushing society towards the post-computing age into a new digital era. The field of AI enables computer systems to behave intelligently and goes beyond numerical computations and manipulations. AI programs focus on problems that require reasoning to solve the problem. The success in solving problems depends naturally on the ability to represent the knowledge about the world that enables the AI to reason with the knowledge to obtain meaningful answers.

AI-based on big data should be applied to its full potential in achieving AI-autonomous credit risk assessment on SME borrower. Technological innovation can optimize the credit risk mechanism to a new level, improve lending efficiency and promote financial inclusion. Conventional risk mechanism in banking may not be sufficient to represent the risky segment of the borrower market. Our proposed solution on knowledge representation of SME creditworthiness can become the basis for building an AI system and mitigate information asymmetry issue in lending.

6.1 Future Research and Limitation

Society 5.0 vision offers an exciting future in enhancing socio-economic development with the help of IR4.0 innovative technology. Developing a complete knowledge representation of creditworthiness requires extensive research. The knowledge model development must consider reusability across different economies and different risk level. Classical or modern theory on the quantitative aspect of creditworthiness knowledge domain has been thoroughly developed by scholars and applied in conventional lending. Future research opens a new opportunity to investigate suitable qualitative aspect and alternative data to supplement hard-financial information for credit assessment. The development of the creditworthiness knowledge model must consider a future empirical study to test the knowledge model in a real-world application.

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